

Bioinformatics and systems biology in the fight against COVID-19

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Abstract

Understanding the virus-host interactions and the molecular disease mechanisms in COVID-19 is essential to develop effective treatment options and successful vaccines. The scientific research community all over the world has sprung into action to aid in the fight against COVID-19. Researchers at the Department of Bioinformatics at Maastricht University (<https://www.maastrichtuniversity.nl/research/bioinformatics>) are at the forefront in curating computer models of COVID-19 molecular processes in the online database WikiPathways founded and maintained by the group (<http://covid.wikipathways.org>). *The initial voluntary effort was a crisis response, and we are excited to announce that it will now be supported by a recently awarded ZonMw COVID-19 grant.* We also joined the international COVID-19 Disease Map project with more than 200 researchers with the aim to create a comprehensive map of the molecular processes of the disease (<https://covid.pages.uni.lu/>). The consortium recently published their first commentary in the Nature journal [Scientific Data](#)¹.

Introduction

The emergence of the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus has caught the world completely unprepared and left the medical systems reeling trying to fight the resulting pandemic. One issue that has made the pandemic so difficult to understand and deal with is the wide range of disease severity and symptoms. COVID-19 infections can result in different patient reactions varying from completely asymptomatic to severe complications resulting in death, yet the reasons for the disparity remain unknown. The overall lack of knowledge about the molecular disease mechanisms also leaves us without an effective treatment or vaccine. The absence of an effective treatment option has left us all stuck quarantining at home in an attempt to prevent the spread of the disease. In a voluntary crisis response, the scientific research community immediately began forming collaborations to work together to better understand COVID-19 and to help find a cure.

New insights emerge daily regarding different stages of COVID-19 infection including virus uptake, virus replication, host immune response and deregulation of other essential processes. For COVID-19, and most other viral infections, sufficiently detailed pathway models to analyse, explain and predict are not yet available. These pathway curation efforts are essential to better understand the exact disease mechanisms. Our department has been a key member of the molecular pathway modelling community for the past ten years, and in an effort to aid in the fight against the COVID-19 pandemic, we have created and contributed to one of the first COVID-19 pathway repositories available, hosted on WikiPathways ².

WikiPathways - a core resource in the COVID-19 Disease Map project

WikiPathways is a freely available database for biological pathway models that is co-maintained by our group at Maastricht University and the Gladstone Institute in San Francisco, California. WikiPathways is built on the same premise as Wikipedia - community curation. Everybody can contribute, curate, discuss and use the entire knowledge base of biological pathways. With over 700 curators around the world, WikiPathways curated pathway collection grows each month,

reaching 1,749 pathways in its last release in June 2020. We also develop bioinformatics tools to analyze and visualize biomedical data to facilitate interpretation of complex disease data. The right hand side of the figure shows an example of such a data visualisation. All tools are freely available including our pathway editor and analysis software, PathVisio³ and relevant apps for Cytoscape (WikiPathways² and CyTargetlinker apps³). Our approaches and workflows can be applied across applications mainly focusing on -omics data analysis. This approach can thus be used in many different research fields producing such omics data. This also made it possible to quickly respond to the new COVID-19 challenge.

Hijack of Ubiquitination by SARS-CoV-2 Pathway

A. Pathway Model

B. Example Data Visualization on Pathway Model

Figure: Hijack of Ubiquitination by SARS-CoV-2 Pathway. **A:** The pathway model (identifier WP4860, <http://www.wikipathways.org/instance/WP4860>) is one of the pathways in the COVID-19 portal on WikiPathways. The rectangles in the figure represent proteins or genes in black, metabolites or drugs in blue, and biological interactions are visualised as arrows. The pathway denotes a potential process carried out by the virus within the human host. In this process, one of the proteins from SARS-CoV-2 virus (Orf10, derived from Open Reading Frame 10) binds to a specific protein complex, thereby altering the activity of the complex, leading to a changed ubiquitination process. **B:** An example of data visualization on the pathway from Figure A, displaying the overall gene expression (in purple) in three different tissue types. Other omics data can also be visualized on this pathway, as well as different variables of interest, such as a comparison in gene expression between two groups (for example, male vs. female, disease vs. healthy, old vs. young, etc.).

Given the novelty of COVID-19, information about the molecular pathways involved was lacking, but new publications with more knowledge arrive daily. The detailed molecular information can be visualized and utilized by the scientific community through the development of pathway models. The WikiPathways team sprung into action when the COVID-19 crisis struck and published the COVID-19 portal in late March 2020 (<http://covid.wikipathways.org/>). By July 2020, the portal already contained 20 detailed molecular pathway models.

Similar initiatives quickly arose, and researchers from many different resources joined the COVID-19 Disease Map Project (<https://covid.pages.uni.lu/>). The project aims to connect and synchronize different resources, align curation efforts and in the end create a comprehensive “molecular map” of the disease. As a collaborative effort, the Disease Maps Project on COVID-19 brings together over 200 researchers working with different tools and platforms to harmonize their efforts, prevent redundancy, and disseminate the information to a broader audience.

Computational approaches from Systems Biology to analyse and interpret COVID-19 data

With the increased availability of detailed molecular pathway information in the Disease Map Project, more extensive pathway curation can be performed and advanced computational analysis approaches can now be applied on the first available COVID-19 patient and experimental data. As more data from COVID-19 studies become available, we can develop better models of virus-host interactions from uptake of the virus to the eventual immune response of the host. Workflows to understand possible treatment options have been developed by our department and utilized when studying other diseases, and they can be applied to COVID-19 data as well. The figure gives an example of a result of such a workflow where it shows how the drug pevonedistat can influence the process described.

Through these approaches and a better understanding of the molecular mechanisms related to COVID-19, we can support the identification of druggable targets, possible drug repurposing and provide leads to better understand why patients have such diverse reactions to the infection. Comprehensive pathway models, extensive molecular data and detailed phenotyped patient data are indispensable for a successful fight against COVID-19.

How you can help

Everyone can get involved in the fight against COVID-19, whether you are a clinician that collects data, a wet lab scientist that performs experiments, or a computational scientist who analyzes data or creates models. Even if you have none of these traditional roles but know your biology, you can simply read the scientific papers coming out and help curate pathways, or download publically available datasets and perform new analysis using the pathways to add to understanding. Of course we are there to help if you do that. Join the pathway model curation efforts and provide expert feedback to pathway modellers. Share your experimental and patient data with COVID-19 researchers so reliable results are obtained and we can get the most out of the available datasets.

References

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